

Appendix S2. Model specifications for statistical analyses.

We estimated components of genetic variance for each trait per environment. In all cases, we used parameter expanded priors to reduce chain mixing times and to prevent the MCMC chains from being stuck at zero. For all traits that were either Gaussian or Poisson distributed, we used “Fisher” parameter expanded priors (see below). To prevent trait distributions from being over-inflated at zero, we filtered our dataset to include only germinated plants. The field population had a ~50% germination rate while the greenhouse population had near 100% germination success. Since the greenhouse population had close to zero variation in germination, we decided it was unnecessary to estimate the genetic variation for germination. For siliques and inflorescences, we further filtered our dataset to only include plants that reached the flowering stage.

To ensure each model cleared all diagnostic criteria (*i.e.*, adequate convergence, >1000 effective sample sizes, autocorrelation <0.1), we ran models for 2,100,000 iterations with a 100,000 burn-in storing samples every 1000 iterations. In the special case of the trait inflorescence, we ran the model for 8,500,000 iterations with a 500,000 burn-in storing samples every 4000 iterations. This was necessary to reduce autocorrelation between posterior estimates. Since stored posteriors produced bimodal distributions, likely as a result of priors pulling estimates toward zero, we obtained estimates of variance using posterior means rather than posterior modes. We used multiple priors in attempt to produce unimodal posteriors, but all posterior distributions tailed towards zero.

For each environment, we obtained estimates of additive genetic variance (V_A), dominance genetic variance (V_D), maternal effect variance (V_M) and residual variance (V_R) using posterior means. Narrow sense heritability (h^2) and the proportion of dominance genetic variance to phenotypic variance ($\frac{V_D}{V_P}$) were calculated from these estimates on both the latent and data scale. We opted not to use deviance information criterion (DIC) values to evaluate the significance of dominance variance, as comparing DIC values is not a perfect model selection criterion especially for non-Gaussian models (Hadfield, 2019). After genetic variance parameters were estimated, test of significance between the two environments as assessed by evaluating overlapping 95% confidence intervals. Confidence intervals that did not overlap indicated significance.

$$h^2 = \frac{V_A}{V_A + V_D + V_M + V_R}$$

$$I_A = \frac{V_A}{\bar{z}^2}$$

Prior for Poisson/Gaussian Traits:

G1: V = 1, nu = 1, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

G2: V = 1, nu = 1, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

G3: V = 1, nu = 1, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

R: V = 1, nu = 0.002

Alternative Priors for Poisson/Gaussian Traits:

G1: V = 1, nu = 0.002, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

G2: V = 1, nu = 0.002, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

G3: V = 1, nu = 0.002, alpha.mu = 0, alpha.V = 1000

R: V = 1, nu = 0.002